

TVR-PA

(Test of Variability Reasoning - Playmobil-based Assessment)

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Please complete the following information:

Age: _____

Gender: Boy / Girl / Other

Grade: _____

Have you ever played with Playmobil? Yes / No

Have you ever designed a custom product or configuration (such as choosing parts, colors, or accessories)? Yes / No

INSTRUCTIONS

This test evaluates your ability to reason about variable configurations. You will be presented with different scenarios with Playmobil figures, objects or toys. Each exercise has 4 options, but only one is correct. You don't need technical knowledge, just look at the options and reason.

Estimated duration: 15-20 minutes.

1. Variation identification

Scenario 1: You see a doctor, a doctor with a coat, and a doctor with a coat and stethoscope

Which feature is common to all configurations?

- a) **Profession**
- b) The coat
- c) The stethoscope
- d) The color of the coat

Scenario 2: You see three Playmobil vehicles: a police motorcycle, a police car and a police van with sirens

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Question: Which feature is common to all configurations?

- a) They all have sirens
- b) They all have the same number of wheels
- c) **They all belong to the police**
- d) They all have rear doors

Scenario 3: You see three Playmobil musicians: a drummer with red jacket and drumsticks, a guitarist with a blue jacket and electric guitar and a singer with a red jacket and microphone

Question: Which feature is common to all configurations?

- a) They all wear red jackets
- b) They all hold an instrument
- c) **They are all musicians**
- d) They all play guitars

2. Configuration validation

Scenario 1: In a coffee shop model: if there's a terrace, it must have an umbrella; if there's a professional coffee machine, there can't be a kitchen.

Question: Which configuration is valid?

- a) **Terrace + umbrella + kitchen**
- b) Terrace + professional coffee machine
- c) Professional coffee machine + kitchen
- d) Terrace + umbrella + professional coffee machine

Scenario 2: In a Playmobil camping set:

- If there is a campfire, there must be a fire extinguisher nearby.
- If there is a tent, there cannot be a caravan.

Question: Which configuration is valid?

- a) **Tent + campfire + fire extinguisher**
- b) Tent + caravan
- c) Campfire + caravan
- d) Tent + campfire

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Scenario 3: In a Playmobil school set:

- If there is a blackboard, there must be at least one piece of chalk.
- If there is a computer, the classroom cannot have a globe.

Question: Which classroom configuration is valid?

- a) Blackboard + desks
- b) Blackboard + chalk**
- c) Computer + globe + desks
- d) Computer + chalk

3. Impact analysis

Scenario 1: What happens if we remove the removable roof from a Playmobil ambulance?

- a) **It is possible to see the interior.**
- b) The emergency logo disappears
- c) The back door stops working
- d) The ambulance loses its wheels

Scenario 2: In a Playmobil pirate ship, what happens if we remove the sail?

- a) **The ship can no longer move using the wind.**
- b) The treasure chest falls over
- c) The pirate loses his sword
- d) The steering wheel disappears

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Scenario 3: In a Playmobil zoo set, a zookeeper forgets to close the gate of the lion enclosure.

Question: What is the most likely consequence?

- a) **The lion escapes from the enclosure**
- b) The lion loses its appetite
- c) The feeding schedule is deleted
- d) The monkey cage is locked

4. Dependency recognition

Scenario 1: Installing solar panels requires a roof.

Question: Which configuration is **invalid**?

- a) **House with solar panels but no roof.**
- b) House with roof and chimney
- c) House with roof and solar panels
- d) House without solar panels or roof

Scenario 2: In a Playmobil firefighter set, using the fire hose requires a water tank.

Question: Which configuration is **invalid**?

- a) **Fire truck with hose but no water tank**
- b) Fire truck with water tank but no hose
- c) Fire truck with hose and water tank
- d) Fire truck with ladder only

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Scenario 3: In a Playmobil medical set, using a stethoscope requires a licensed medical professional.

Question: Which configuration is **invalid**?

- a) **Receptionist with a stethoscope**
- b) Paramedic with a stethoscope
- c) Doctor with a stethoscope
- d) Nurse with a thermometer

5. Variant comparison

Scenario 1: Compare a firefighter with helmet and hose vs. a female firefighter with walkie-talkie and helmet.

Question: How do they **differ**?

- a) **In the accessories they carry**
- b) In the use of helmet
- c) In the type of uniform
- d) In their profession

Scenario 2: Compare two Playmobil chefs:

- One is baking a cake and holding a whisk
- The other is grilling meat and holding tongs

Question: How do they **differ**?

- a) **In the tools they use**
- b) In their profession
- c) In the location of their restaurant
- d) In the color of their chef hat

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Scenario 3: Compare two Playmobil construction workers:

- One is operating a jackhammer and wearing ear protection
- The other is carrying bricks and wearing a hard hat

Question: How do they **differ**?

- a) In the tools they use**
- b) In their profession
- c) In the color of their boots
- d) In the shape of their helmet

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SELF-ASSESSMENT

- Did you find the test easy or difficult (mark from 0 to 10)?
- Do you think you could design a toy with different versions?
- Would you like to do this with your classmates?

END OF TEST

Thank you for your participation. This test will help us understand how you reason about variable systems. Your feedback and results are very important for further improvement.